

UNDERSTANDING THE BEHAVIOUR OF FIBRE METAL LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO LOCALISED BLAST LOADING

S.L.Lemanski¹, G.N.Nurick¹, G.S.Langdon^{1,2}, M.S.Simmons², W.J.Cantwell², G.K.Schleyer²

¹*Blast Impact and Survivability Research Unit (BISRU), Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Cape Town, Private Bag, Rondebosch 7701, South Africa*

²*Impact Research Centre, Department of Engineering, Brownlow Hill, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, L69 3GH, United Kingdom
e-mail: gnurick@ebe.uct.ac.za*

SUMMARY: This paper examines the behaviour of Fibre Metal Laminates (FML's) subjected to localised explosive blast loading. Experiments are conducted on samples of varying thickness and material distribution. Plastic deformation, debonding, delamination, fibre fracture and matrix cracking have all been identified as energy absorption mechanisms. Widespread debonding is particularly evident between layers. Comparison between different plates of similar overall thickness shows no significant improvement in blast performance with increasing number of distinct material layers. This suggests that debonding does not absorb a significant proportion of the blast energy.

KEYWORDS: Fibre-Metal Laminate, Plate, Blast loading, Failure

INTRODUCTION

A common method of protecting people and/or objects from the effect of a blast event is to deploy some form of plate like structure between the blast source and the object to be protected. In general, clamped metal plates subjected to *localised* blast loads deform plastically until some threshold impulse is reached. If this threshold impulse is exceeded, tearing occurs at the centre, usually resulting in a small cap or petalled tearing pattern. Langdon, Cantwell and Nurick [1, 2] identified some typical damage regimes of fibre-metal laminates. Delamination and debonding were found through the cross sections of the plates, and rupture of the back face occurred.

Fibre-Metal Laminates (FML's) are lightweight blast-resistant materials that consist of several composite layers sandwiched between metallic sheets. They were identified as promising materials for lightweight blast resistant applications [1-3]. This study presents the results of blast loading carried out on FML's made from layers of Twintex (woven glass fibres in a thermoplastic resin) and rolled aluminium. Several variables affect the FML behaviour, including plate thickness, plate composition (thickness and distribution of the aluminium and composite layers in the plate), plate area, and loading diameter.

NOMENCLATURE

Several plate configurations are tested, which are identified according to AXYZ-#

where A refers to Aluminium
T refers to Twintex
X the number of layers of aluminium. The aluminium layers are spaced equally through the thickness of the laminate, with one aluminium layer on the front face and one on the back face.
Y the number of layers of Twintex. The layers of Twintex are all of equal thickness, and each Twintex layer is placed between the aluminium layers.
Z the number of sheets of glass fibre cloth are used in each layer of Twintex.
the plate number.

Table 1: Plate thickness groupings

Group	Number of layers in plate
O	<6
A	6-10
B ₁ } B	11-15
B ₂ }	16
C ₁ } C	19
C ₂ }	22
D	28

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The fibre metal laminates investigated in this study are manufactured at the University of Liverpool from 0.6mm thick aluminium alloy (2024-0) and a Twintex composite (woven glass fibres in a polypropylene matrix). Panel manufacture is described more fully by Lemanski *et al* [4].

Numerous studies have investigated the localised blast loading of flat plates, for example as presented in [1-2, 4-10]. The same general procedure has been adopted in this investigation. The plates are clamped between two steel clamping frames, leaving an exposed area of 300mm x 300mm. This is mounted onto a ballistic pendulum, by which means the explosive impulse can be measured. A localised blast loading is obtained by detonating a disc of PE4 plastic explosive on a polystyrene pad in the centre of the plate. The experimental setup prior to blasting is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Ballistic pendulum setup

OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION

Front face deformations

The front faces of the plates are often heavily pitted in the region where the explosive is mounted. This can be seen in all front face pictures (Figures 2-4). The pitting is predominantly a surface effect, and is distinct from the plate deformation that is discussed elsewhere in this paper. The pitting is seen on all the front faces, but its severity appears to be primarily a function of charge mass.

In some cases, an area of the front face undergoes local plastic deformation as a result of the blast impulse, leaving a crater shaped front face deformation, or “ring buckle”. This ring buckle is shown clearly in Figures 2.c-d, 3.c and 4. Thicker plates have larger bending stiffness, and generally exhibit this cratering more distinctly than thinner plates, which tend instead to exhibit global plate bending.

Back face deformations

A diamond or cross-shaped permanent deflection is seen on the rear face of the plate, examples of which are shown in Figure 2. The deformation remains orthotropic if back face tearing occurs, as seen in Figures 3.b-d. The woven Twintex fabric is aligned so that the fibres are oriented parallel to the edges of the plates, and the diamond pattern therefore develops because the wave speed in the fibres is larger than in the resin, allowing the explosive shock wave to travel faster in the fibre direction. Some panels are manufactured with Twintex fabric oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the edges of the plates. As expected, the deflection pattern on the back faces of these panels is rotated through 45° , as shown in Figure 4.

Fig.2. Photographs showing front face deformation, cross section and back face deformation of plates without back face tearing

Fig. 3: Photographs showing front face, cross section and back face of plates exhibiting back face tearing

Fig. 4: Photograph showing front face deformation, cross section and back face deformation of Group C plate (A4T36-7) with 45° Twintex lay-up

Observation of plate behaviour and damage mechanisms

The differences in composition and structure of FML's and monolithic plates (such as steel) allow energy to be dissipated via different mechanisms. Reyes and Cantwell [10] and Zhu et al [11] reported that laminated composite materials can dissipate energy through debonding, delamination and matrix cracking.

Different plate behaviours (e.g. front and back face deflections) are characterised by the nominal plate thickness or the number of layers. Plates are divided into the different groups shown in Table 1 according to number of layers to characterise various aspects of plate behaviour [4, 7].

Fig 5: Plates of different thickness subjected to ~15 Ns blast impulse.

Figure 2 shows photographs of plates of different thicknesses subjected to an impulse of approximately 15 Ns. Thinner plates exhibit onset of back face tearing at lower impulses [8] than thicker plates. Thus, for the thicker plates shown in Figure 5 (A3T28, A4T34) the 15 Ns impulse causes large plastic deformation, while for thinner plates (A5T42, A2T12) this causes tearing and subsequent petalling.

The cross sections shown in Figures 2 and 3, indicate that thin plates (Groups A, B₁) typically show no significant difference between front and back face deflections. For thick plates (Groups B₂, C₁, C₂, D), the front face often exhibits only small deflections – even if the back face deflection is large. Figures 2.c,d show that the back face commonly debonds from the rest of the plate and undergoes large plastic deformation, while the main part of the plate experiences relatively small deflections.

The cross sections presented in Figures 2-5 show that interlaminar debonding occurs at the aluminium-Twintex interfaces. In general, thinner panels experience global deformation through the entire thickness and only a small amount of debonding, while thicker panels experience widespread debonding and small deformations (apart from the debonded back face). Debonding is usually the first damage mechanism to be seen, occurring even at low impulses. For a given panel configuration, debonding damage spreads over a larger area as the explosive impulse increases.

As the impulse increases towards the tearing threshold impulse for a particular plate, delaminations also become evident within the Twintex layers. Matrix cracking and fibre fracture are also seen in the Twintex close to the blast. These damage mechanisms are seen before onset of back face tearing in Figures 2.a,b and also in Figure 5 (plates A3T28 and A4T34).

Figures 3 and 5 show that the damage mechanisms apparent during large plastic deformation (i.e. debonding, delamination, matrix cracking, fibre fracture) are still evident when plates undergo back face tearing. Tensile tearing occurs on the back face of the plate because the local curvature leads to greater material strains on the back face than on the front face.

For impulses that only just exceed the tearing threshold of the plate, only a small tear or cap is seen in the back face, e.g. Figure 3.c, and Figure 5 (plate A5T42). When the blast impulse is higher, petalling is observed on the back face (e.g. Figure 3.a,b,d). As the blast impulse increases further, petalling occurs over a larger area and throughout the thickness of the plate, e.g. Figure 3.a, and Figure 5 (plate A2T12).

At low impulses, plastic deformation, debonding and matrix cracking are the damage mechanisms usually seen in FML's. Delamination within the macroscopically homogeneous Twintex layers only usually occurs with larger blasts, while fibre pull-out begins shortly before tensile tearing of the back face that is associated with plate rupture.

Explanation of plate behaviour

Although the relative importance of the different energy absorption mechanisms has not been quantified, these results suggest that interlaminar debonding is not a significant energy absorption mechanism. References [10, 11] suggest that inter-laminar debonding is not a significant energy

absorption mechanism. Both studies concluded that local deflection and fibre failure are the major energy absorbing mechanisms. Of all the tests performed, the largest possible proportion of energy absorbed by debonding occurs for plate A4T32-2, as this was the test for which the ratio of interfaces to charge mass was the greatest. The following approximation confirms that debonding is only a minor energy absorption mechanism:

Energy released by PE4 explosive [12]:	6 kJ/g	
<u>Amount of explosive used in test:</u>	<u>2 g</u>	
Total energy released:	12 kJ	
Energy absorbed debonding Al-Twintex interface [3]:	3 kJ/m ²	
Exposed area of plate (0.3m x 0.3m):	0.09 m ²	
<u>Number of interfaces for A4T32 panel:</u>	<u>6</u>	
Total energy that can be absorbed by debonding:	1.62 kJ	(upper limit)

Thus, no more than 13.5% of the blast energy can be absorbed by interlaminar debonding. Because the calculation assumes that all interfaces fully debond over the entire exposed area of the plate, this is an upper limit on the percentage of blast energy that can be absorbed.

Franz, Nurick and Perry [8] investigated the response of layered glass fibre laminates to blast loading. Since the above calculations have established that debonding is not a significant energy absorption mechanism, reference [8] is used to provide an explanation of FML behaviour. It was found that the layers on the back face provide structural support to the layers on the front face, and this can be used as the basis for the following qualitative explanation of FML response.

For thin plates, it is observed that the blast energy causes deformation throughout the thickness of the plate because the layers towards the back of the plate offer little structural support to the layers in front. Because the overall bending stiffness of the plate is low, less energy is required to bend the whole plate than to debond the back layers from the front. Similar sized deformations are seen on both the front and back faces of the plate.

For thick plates, it is frequently observed that the back face experienced significantly larger inelastic deformations than the front face. This is because the layers at the front of the plate are supported by the layers behind. Because the overall bending stiffness of the plate is high, less energy is required to debond the back layers than is required to deform the whole plate. The back face therefore debonds from the rest of the plate and its deformations are larger than those of the front face.

Comparison of plates with different material distribution

The dimensionless tearing threshold impulses of plates with different numbers of interfaces but similar overall thickness are compared. Table 2 compares A4T32 with A2T18 (both 10 layers) and A3T26 with A4T34 (with 15 and 16 layers respectively). These comparisons show only very slight improvement in blast performance for plates with more interfaces – which is consistent with slightly increased energy absorbed by interlaminar debonding.

Table 2: Comparison of tearing thresholds

Plate configuration	Number of layers	Proportion of Aluminium (% by thickness)	Dimensionless threshold impulse
A2T18	10	22.4	3.9
A4T32	10	43.0	4.0
A3T26	15	22.4	2.6
A4T34	16	29.0	3.0

CONCLUSIONS

The work presented describes the response of fibre metal laminates (FML's) to localised blast loading. Plate behaviour is found to be highly dependent upon plate thickness. The results show that, in general, thicker panels exhibit smaller deflections for a given impulse and exhibit higher tearing thresholds than thin panels. Thick and thin panels exhibit different front and back face deflections. Thin panels show little debonding, while thicker panels have larger debonded areas. This is because as bending stiffness increases with increasing panel thickness, debonding becomes an easier failure mechanism compared to global plate bending.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the Leverhulme Trust (UK), the Royal Commission for the Exhibition of 1851 (UK), the National Research Foundation (SA), the EPSRC (UK) for financing this research, and acknowledge BP, Gluco, Linpac and the Royal Mail for their support

The authors also wish to thank L. Watkins, G. Newins, and H. Emmerich at the University of Cape Town, and P. Smith and C. Eyre at the University of Liverpool for their technical assistance. The authors also wish to thank S. Chung Kim Yuen for his contribution to this work.

REFERENCES

1. Langdon, G.S., Cantwell, W.J. and Nurick, G.N., "The blast response of novel thermoplastic-based fibre-metal laminates – some preliminary results and observations", *Composites Science and Technology*, 65, pp. 861-872, 2005.
2. Langdon, G.S., Cantwell, W.J. and Nurick, G.N., "The blast performance of novel fibre metal laminates", *Proc. Structures Under Shock and Impact Conference VIII*, pp. 455-464, 2004.
3. Reyes, G. and Cantwell, W.J., "The mechanical properties of fibre-metal laminates based on glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene", *Composites Science and Technology*, 60, pp.1085-1094, 2000.
4. Lemanski, S.L., Nurick, G.N., Langdon, G.S., Simmons, M.C., Cantwell, W.J., Schleyer, G.K., "Behaviour of fibre-metal laminates subjected to localised blast loading: Part I –

Experimental Observations”, *Int. Journal of Impact Engineering* (in preparation for submission 2005).

5. Nurick, G.N. and Shave, G.C., “The deformation and tearing of thin square plates subjected to impulsive loads - an experimental study”, *Int. Journal of Impact Engineering*, 18, pp. 99-116, 1996.

6. Nurick, G.N., Martin, J.B., “Deformation of Thin Plates Subjected to Impulsive Loading – A Review; Part II: Experimental Studies”, *Int. Journal of Impact Engineering*, 8, pp 159-170, 1989.

7. Lemanski, S.L., Nurick, G.N., Langdon, G.S., Simmons, M.C., Cantwell, W.J., Schleyer, G.K., “Behaviour of fibre-metal laminates subjected to localised blast loading: Part III – Quantitative Analysis”, *Int. Journal of Impact Engineering* (in preparation for submission 2005).

8. Franz, T., Nurick, G.N., Perry, M.J., “Experimental investigation into the response of chopped-strand mat glassfibre laminates to blast loading”, *Int. Journal of Impact Engineering*, 27, pp. 639-667, 2002.

9. Jacob, N., Chung Kim Yuen, S., Nurick, G. N., Bonorchis, D., Desai, S. A., Tait, D., “Scaling aspects of quadrangular plates subjected to localised blast loads—experiments and predictions”, *Int. Journal of Impact Engineering*, 30, pp. 1179-1208, 2004.

10. Reyes, G. and Cantwell, W.J., “The high velocity impact response of composite and FML-reinforced sandwich structures”, *Composites Science and Technology*, 64, pp. 35-54, 2004.

11. Zhu, G., Goldsmith, W. and Dharan, C.K.H., “Penetration of laminated Kevlar by projectiles – I. Experimental investigation”, *Int. Journal of Solids and Structures*, 29, pp. 399-420, 1992.

12. Cooper, P.W. and Kurowski, S.R., “Introduction to the technology of explosives”, Wiley-VCH, 1996.